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E-LEARNER in Scientific Discourse: A Corpus Based Analysis

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Scientific discourse represents specific knowledge from different types of scientific activities. This type of discourse is rather unique (Маслова 2013) as it actually arises as a response to numerous social issues, questions and concerns. It can be traced in scientific discourse devoted to investigations of different teaching and learning modes which are popular right now due to changes in society during pandemic time.

Scientific discourse is studied through the corpus which comprises 28 articles devoted to e-learning. All the articles have been chosen from Scopus and Web of Science sites. The criterion for the choice of articles is the lexeme E-LEARNING either in the title or among key words. Sketch Engine has been used to process the created corpus.

E-LEARNING is a method of learning that involves studying at home using a computer and the Internet (<https://www.ldoceonline.com/dictionary/e-learning>). E-learning can also be termed as a network enabled transfer of skills and knowledge, and the delivery of education is made to a large number of recipients at the same or different times. Earlier, it was not accepted wholeheartedly as it was assumed that this system lacked the human element required in learning (<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/definition/e-learning>). However, the concept of e-learning embracing various spheres of education, business, medicine, services and other social sectors as well as individual teaching and learning is connected with new possibilities to get educated.

As the topic of all articles is e-learning, the active participant of teaching process is an e-learner. E-learners are defined as students who take advantage of learning that is usually Internet-based learning, but could be any electronically enhanced learning; e-learners are technology savvy, motivated, and self-directed (IGI-Global Dictionary).

The most frequently used keywords in the corpus that correspond to the definitions of E-LEARNING and E-LEARNER are hypermedia, internet-based and Moodle (see Picture 1) which describe the process of e-learning.

Word	Word
1 e-learning	11 educ
2 elearning	12 uhvrxufhv
3 wkh	13 delone
4 itss	14 lmss
5 hypermedia	15 internet-based
6 dqg	16 e-learners
7 adaptive	17 lms
8 e-issn	18 procedia
9 lto	19 moodle
10 soa	20 conjoint

Picture 1. Mostly frequent keywords in the corpus

Our research concentrates on the lemma E-LEARNER that is on the 16th position among mostly frequently used words in the corpus.

The following N-gram demonstrates E-LEARNER collocational patterns used in the articles selected (see Picture 2).

Picture 2. N-gram of collocations with E-LEARNER

Collocational patterns consisting of a verb with E-LEARNER as subject are not numerous indicating that e-learners are rather seldom shown as active agents in the corpus and are presented by structures E-LEARNER+say, E-LEARNER+adopt: E-learning systems usage is also positively influenced by information quality (H2a) and by collaboration quality (H4a), meaning that e-learners adopt these systems derived from the importance and adequacy of the contents, also derived from the collaboration with their colleagues and the overall satisfaction, similar results were found in other studies. The absence of

E-LEARNER as an active agent shows that studies are concentrated on other issues what can be seen from the N-gram (see Picture 1) on the one hand, and on the other, it is due to peculiarities of the scientific style writing. Thus, the nouns modified by E-LEARNER: E-LEARNER+relation / autonomy / isolation / perception objective / satisfaction as well as the structure E-LEARNER'S+satisfaction / performance / provenience / participation / characterization / benefit / feedback / usage / level delineate the objects of most research dealing with e-learning.

The contextual interpretation analysis enables to define most frequently discussed topics in the corpus of articles which are presented in the following table (see Table 1).

Table 1. Subjects of investigations presented in the corpus

Subjects	Examples
Types of e-learners	They further argued that, the most outstanding common characteristic of many e-Learning systems is that they encourage an inert e-learner; a fact attributed to the lack of synchronous interactive capabilities that are the trademark of learner-tutor and learner-learner interaction.
E-learner's skills	... team collaboration, e-learner autonomy, motivation and interest as well as e-learner relations with team members, with the e-tutor, and the society in which he/she exists.
E-learner's space	When this feedback is lacking the possible result is e-learner isolation, which leads to other problems like high dropout rate, unmet pedagogical needs, and negative perceptions among peers and employers who consider e-Learning as second-rate education.
E-learning characteristics	... the course structure, content format, content presentation, learning context and processes, instructional tools, e-learner objectives, e-learner perceptions, cognitive learning styles, interaction and communication amongst e-Learning participants, team collaboration

The further research will concentrate on the lemma LEARNER with frequency use 276 in the same corpus.